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STUDIES OF THE PROBLEM OF STRESS AND STRESS RESISTANCE OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: The problem of stress and stress tolerance of junior students is studied. The results of the study established the importance of stress resistance, causes and methods of dealing with stress in the period after the winter examination session; the values of stress resistance after the winter session among female respondents are worse than those of male respondents.

Keywords: stress, stress tolerance, students, session

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СТРЕССА И СТРЕССОУСТОЙЧИВОСТИ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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Аннотация: Изучена проблема стресса и стрессоустойчивости студентов младших курсов. В результатах проведенного исследования установлено значение стрессоустойчивости, причины и методы борьбы со стрессом в период после зимней экзаменационной сессии; значения стрессоустойчивости после зимней сессии среди респондентов женского пола хуже, чем у респондентов мужского пола.

Ключевые слова: стресс, стрессоустойчивость, студенты, сессия

Relevance. Students experience high intellectual and emotional stress in the process of studying at the university. Currently, the student has great resources for development. However, young students have a number of individual psychological characteristics that can prevent them from fully solving this task. Problems with finances, housing conditions, self-catering, difficulty with processing a large amount of information are the companions of student life. Most students do not know how to fully control themselves in stressful situations in educational activities and in the household sphere. Among the most important problems faced by students is the problem of experiencing exam stress [1-3].

Stress is a functional state of the body that occurs as a result of an external negative impact on its mental functions, nervous processes or the activity of peripheral organs.

Manifestations of stress: deterioration of memory and attention, decreased creativity, difficulty concentrating, anxiety, mood swings, feelings of depression and loneliness, health problems, poor or increased appetite, excessive or insufficient sleep and emotional manifestations (irritability, aggression).

Stressors are factors that cause the development of a stress reaction.

Stress tolerance in students is a complex personality trait, which is characterized by the necessary adaptation of the student to the effects of external and internal factors in the process of educational activity.

Levels of stress resistance according to Hans Selye:

High level of stress resistance. A person remains calm under any circumstances, even those in which the majority will panic. By virtue of experience and self-improvement, such a person has learned to cope with

stress in any form. It is much easier for such people to minimize the consequences of unpleasant events.

The average level of stress resistance. A person with an average level of stress tolerance is able to withstand problems and troubles, although after a certain time, but releases critical situations. He does not panic and is able to soberly assess the problem.

Low degree of stress resistance. This level is typical for anxious individuals with an increased emotional background. Such people perceive most stressful situations as posing a threat to their safety. In a stressful situation, reactions manifest themselves in the form of anxiety, mental and physical stress. Anxiety is accompanied by a violation of the ability to analyze, a low degree of concentration of attention. This level of stress resistance is dangerous due to the occurrence of various psychosomatic diseases.

Extremely low degree of stress resistance. In stressful situations, such people are unable to control themselves. Stress for such people affects all body systems. The body of people with an extremely low degree of stress resistance wears out 40% faster than people who live in peace.

Goal. To study the problem of stress and stress tolerance of junior students.

Materials and methods of research. Comparative-evaluative, analytical and evaluative methods were used in the work. An anonymous questionnaire was conducted aimed at obtaining information about the levels of stress tolerance among students, the causes and methods of overcoming stress. The obtained data were processed statistically. The respondents were undergraduate students of the Medical University aged 17-20 years. The study was conducted at the beginning of the spring semester.

Results and their discussion. After the winter holidays, 5.7% of students have a high level of stress tolerance and, consequently, good adaptive skills; 64.4% of students have an average level of stress tolerance; 26.9% of students have a low level of stress tolerance; 2.8% of students have an extremely low level of stress tolerance, which indicates serious problems with adaptation and a "premorbid state".

By gender, the division is as follows: among girls, 2.4% have a high level of stress resistance, 68% have an average level of stress resistance, 26% have a low level of stress resistance, 3.7% have a very low

level of stress resistance. Among young men, 17% have a high level of stress resistance, 50% have an average level of stress resistance, 30% have a low level of stress resistance, 0% have a very low level of stress resistance.

Based on the survey data, it can be concluded that most of the students have an average level of stress tolerance. Young men turned out to be the most stress-resistant.

According to the survey results, the most popular methods of dealing with stress are:

Destructive ways of overcoming stress among students and female students are as follows: delicious food is in the first place (71%), aggression is in the second (16.3%), smoking is in the third (12.5%).

Constructive ways to overcome stress among students and female students are as follows: in the first place – sleep / rest (41.3%) and communication with friends and family (41.3%), in the second – analysis of their actions (17.3%).

The results of a survey of stressful situations in students' academic activities: final work not completed on time – 13.4%, examination session – 71.1%, heavy academic load – 11.5%, lack of interest in the discipline – 2%, disappointment in the future profession – 2%.

The results of the survey of stressful situations in personal life: illness or death of family members – 76.9%; conflicts with classmates and loved ones – 3.8%; relocation – 3.8%; problems in relationships with the second half – 11.5%; health problems – 3.8%.

The most frequent manifestations of learning stress are poor sleep – 67.3%, a feeling of constant lack of time – 10.5%, increased fatigue – 7.6%. The least frequent – health disorders – 3.8%, violation of social contacts – 3.8%.

Conclusion. The results of the study established the importance of stress resistance, causes and methods of dealing with stress in the period after the winter examination session; the values of stress resistance after the winter session among female respondents are worse than those of male respondents. It can be concluded that students tend to overcomplicate everything to a greater extent. Based on the results of the study, it is possible to make personal recommendations to respondents to maintain and improve stress tolerance.

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